

Ons kenmerk

BrfIRELIANCE28jan26

Betreft

Expression of Interest and Support for the Horizon Europe
Project iRELIANCE

Datum / Plaats

28 Jan 2026 / Nieuwegein

Bijlage(n)

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To whom it may concern,

RIWA-Rijn, based in the Netherlands, has been informed by KWR about the Horizon Europe project iRELIANCE.

The iRELIANCE project aims to develop knowledge, methodologies, and decision-support tools to enable effective cross-sectoral decision-making for water–energy–food–ecosystem (WEFE) resource management at river basin scale, under conditions of deep climate, socio-economic, and geopolitical uncertainty, with the ultimate objective of strengthening water systems resilience.

The objectives of iRELIANCE, as well as the knowledge and tools it seeks to generate, are of strategic relevance to RIWA-Rijn, particularly in light of the new European Water Resilience Strategy and the increasing challenges posed by climate change, extreme events, competing water uses and, in recent times, geopolitical instability. These developments require new approaches to long-term strategic planning and operational decision-making that explicitly address uncertainty and cross-sectoral interdependencies.

In this context, the iRELIANCE project is both timely and critically important. The project's focus on integrated, participatory, and scenario-based approaches for decision-making under deep uncertainty can provide valuable support to long-term strategic planning for water systems; operational decision-making under uncertainty; cross-sectoral dialogue among water, energy, agriculture, and ecosystem actors; informed discussions with governmental bodies and relevant agencies on policy development; transparent and equitable discussions with water users on water allocation, use, and availability.

Accordingly, RIWA-Rijn hereby expresses its interest and willingness to contribute to the iRELIANCE project through the following activities, as relevant to the Rhine River basin:

- engaging in content-related discussions and workshops for the co-creation of knowledge, methodologies, and decision-support tools;
- contributing expertise, insights, and feedback from practice to ensure the relevance and applicability of project outputs;
- mobilising our network to support stakeholder engagement, data collection, sharing of lessons learned, and uptake of project results;
- participating in the validation and testing of iRELIANCE knowledge, tools, and approaches;
- supporting the dissemination and exploitation of project results for policy, planning, and practice.

We believe that collaboration within the iRELIANCE project can create significant added value, both for the project and for our organisation, by strengthening evidence-based and inclusive approaches to resilient water and related resource management.

We look forward to future collaboration with the iRELIANCE consortium and remain available for any further information or clarification.

Kind regards,

Dr. Gerard J. Stroomberg

Directeur

RIWA-Rijn